

ENERGY MONITORING DASHBOARD

Online energy monitoring and forecasting tool
for ski areas and their energy suppliers

WHAT ARE THE ADVANTAGES OF THE DASHBOARD?

For ski areas:

Comprehensive monitoring and visualisation of energy flows

Minimisation of electricity costs through

- Increasing energy efficiency
- Reduction of peak loads

Minimisation of the CO₂ footprint

For the energy supplier:

Consumption forecasts and use of data in energy trading

WHAT CAN THE DASHBOARD DO?

- ✓ Visualisation of energy flows:
Enables all metering points to be available on the following day
- ✓ Detection of load peaks: Displays on the basis of quarter-hourly consumption values
- ✓ Forecasting tool: system planning (particularly relevant during the snowmaking season)
No installation of additional hardware is necessary.

Optional: Monitoring and visualisation of live data by means of a hardware controller

THAT SOUNDS PERFECT! WHAT'S NEXT?

Arrange a first consultation appointment with the NEFI team!

Step 1: The dashboard is adapted to your ski area.

Step 2: Implementation takes place together with your energy supplier. Relevant interfaces - if they do not already exist - are set up. No additional hardware is required.

You always have an overview of the energy flows of your entire ski area and can reduce your energy costs through targeted measures.

Our
contact details:
office@nefi.at
www.nefi.at/en/
www.vorzeigeregion-energie.at

www.nefi.at/en/solutions